

The Absence of the Jewish Usurer Trope in the Andalusī Written Sources

Adday Hernández

Starting in the twelfth century, usury became one of the immoral activities attributed to the Jews in Christian anti-Jewish propaganda. Jews became so commonly associated with usury in the Latin-Christian world that the word “Jew” itself became a synonym for “usurer”, mainly in the texts of the Christian exegetes. While this trope spread over space and time, it does not seem to have existed in al-Andalus.

In Islamic texts, while some examples associate *ribā* (usury) with Jews, it is equally attributed to Christians. Moreover, the practice of usury does not seem to have been used as an argument against the Jews in Muslim polemical literature. This paper focuses on the Andalusī context, showing how the trope of the Jewish usurer did not take root in Muslim Iberia as it did among the Christians of the Peninsula. Of special interest are developments that took place in the Naṣrid kingdom, where several legal opinions (*fatāwā*) issued between the eighth/fourteenth and the ninth/fifteenth centuries reveal a concern among the population about loans at interest issued by Jews. The Naṣrid jurists, however, appear to have tolerated these interfaith activities.

Keywords: Usury, *Ribā*, *Dhimmī*-s, Jews, al-Andalus, Alterity, Interconfessional relations

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Usurious transactions, and the lending of money at interest in general, are activities subject to distrust and even prohibition in the three monotheistic religions, with arguments that share some common features, as we shall see. In the medieval Latin-Christian world such activities were often negatively associated with the Jews. Did the same association exist in al-Andalus? The aim of this contribution is not to assess whether or not Jews in al-Andalus lent money at interest – some of them may have done so, just as some Christians and Muslims may have too, in spite of the extant theoretical prohibitions in their respective normative religious and legal traditions. The aim, rather, is to explore to what extent the trope of the Jewish usurer was employed in al-Andalus, as compared with the Iberian Christian context, where we know that it was widespread.

In the Islamic tradition, the issue of usury is generally discussed in relation to the term *ribā*. In the first section (*Ribā* and usury), I will first deal with the ban on *ribā* in the two main sources of Islamic law (the Qur’ān and the *Sunna*), and then with similarities and differences regarding the legislation on usury in Judaism and Christianity, while at the same time addressing the issue of how to understand exactly what is being banned. Both *ribā* and usury were in fact not static normative concepts and the ambiguities and changes in their understanding need to be taken into account. The second section focuses on the extent to which non-Muslims and more specifically Jews are mentioned in Andalusī legal works as being involved in the practice of *ribā*. The analysis of such examples in the social and historical circumstances in which they are located – while also taking into account what is known about other regions of the Islamic world – allows some conclusions to be drawn as to why the trope of the Jewish usurer was largely absent in al-Andalus.

Ribā and usury

The translation of the Arabic term *ribā* as “usury” has been widely discussed. Neither of these two terms are static, as their meaning and the activities they refer to have been subject to change, but basically both terms describe practices perceived as involving unjust financial gain.² While in early periods both “*ribā*” and “usury” were mainly used

¹ This article has been made possible thanks to a Juan de la Cierva – Incorporación (IJCI-2017-31351) postdoctoral contract, supervised by Maribel Fierro and funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities (2019-2021). It forms part of the project *Teología, pensiero economico e prassi commerciali: feneratio, ribā e tasso d’interesse fra cristianesimo e islam* (Theology, economic thought and commercial practices: *feneratio, ribā* and interest rate in Christianity and Islam), funded by Fondazione per le Scienze Religiose (Fscire) and Banca d’Italia. In it I develop, with new materials and textual evidence, my preliminary findings presented in Adday Hernández, “La imagen del otro. La visión de cristianos y musulmanes respecto al judío y la usura en el s. XII”, *Fronteras en discusión: La península Ibérica en el siglo XII*, ed. Juan Martos and Marisa Bueno (Madrid: Almudayna, 2012), 133–42. English reviewed by Nicholas Callaway.

² I am taking this expression from Mohamad Fadel, “Ribā, Efficiency and Prudential Regulation: Preliminary Thoughts”, *Wisconsin Journal of International Law* 25 (2008), 655–702, 655. Fadel refers to Frank E. Vogel; Samuel

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to refer to any kind of interest coming from a loan, the progressive acceptance of interest eventually led to changes in their definition, which came to refer only to specific activities or excessive interest rates.³

The origin, development and evolution of the juridical doctrine banning usury/*ribā/neshekh-ribbit* is similar in the three monotheistic religions, and diverse – and even contradictory – juridical opinions have coexisted in the three traditions. Moreover, an overview of the regulations on usury in Judaism, Christianity and Islam reveals that, at some point, all three considered usury at least as a reprehensible and immoral activity without actually defining its exact meaning.⁴ For example, in Islam we find several Prophetic traditions comparing *ribā* with incest: “*There are seventy-two types of ribā, the least of which is like a man committing incest with his mother.*”⁵

In spite of the general moral opposition, though, lending money at interest to people outside one’s own religion has been tolerated by some authorities in all three monotheistic religions, as we shall see. This permissive opinion might have offered special opportunities for the Jews, since after they lost political control and started living as a minority among either Muslims or Christians, they were always surrounded by a non-Jewish population.

The prohibition of *ribā* in Islam and the role of non-Muslims

The ban on *ribā* appears already in the Qur’ān and the *Sunna*, but it was the jurists who carried out the task of explaining what could and could not be performed by Muslims.

The semantic root *r-b-w* appears twenty times in the Qur’ān in eight different forms, always in relation to the increase of something, but only thirteen of those references are related to economic issues.⁶ *Ribā* is forbidden in four different qur’anic *ayāt* (chronologically 30: 39; 3: 130; 4: 161; 2: 275-281)⁷ and some scholars such as Joseph Schacht have detected a tightening of the prohibition with the passage of time.⁸

L. Hayes, *Islamic Law and Finance. Religion, risk and return* (The Hague, Boston: Kluwer Law International, 1998), and Nabil A. Saleh, *Unlawful Gain and Legitimate Profit in Islamic law. Ribā, gharar and Islamic banking* (London: Graham & Trotman, 1992).

³ Although the first allusions to *ribā* in the Qur’ān seem to refer to specific activities, the term was later understood by most jurists as the charging of any kind of interest. After that, the acceptance by certain legal opinions of the interest charged in commercial transactions (and not in loans) led to the debate on the suitability of translating the term *ribā* as “unlawful gain/profit”.

⁴ Among the many publications on this topic in Judaism, Christianity and Islam, see, for instance, David J. Jones, *Reforming the Morality of Usury. A Study of Differences that Separated the Protestant Reformers* (Dallas, Lanham, Boulder, New York, Oxford: University Press of America, 2004); Vincent J. Cornell, “In the Shadow of Deuteronomy. Approaches to interest and usury in Judaism and Christianity”, *Interest in Islamic Economics*, ed. Abdulkader Thomas (London, New York: Routledge, 2006), 13–26; Ezra Basri, *The Laws of Interest* (Jerusalem: Haktav Institute, 1987); Salo Wittmayer Baron, “The Economic Views of Maimonides”, *Essays on Maimonides. An octocentennial volume* (New York: Columbia University Press, 1941), 127–226, 211.

⁵ This hadith, with some variations, is included in the collection of Ibn Māja. Ibn Māja, *Sunan - Jam‘ jawāmi‘ al-ahādīth wa-al-asānīd wa-maknaz al-ṣiḥāh wa-al-sunan wa-al-masānīd* (Vaduz, Liechtenstein, Cairo: Jam‘iyat al-maknaz al-islāmī (Thesaurus Islamicus Foundation), 2000-2001), [2360], 329.

⁶ El-Said M. Badawi *et al.*, *Arabic-English Dictionary of Qur’anic Usage* (Leiden: Brill, 2008), 345–6.

⁷ See Sayyid Tahir, “The Qur’ān and *ribā*”, *Qur’anic Horizons* 1/2 (1996), 30–56; Ziauddin Ahmad, “The Qur’anic theory of *ribā*”, *Islamic Quarterly* 20-22 (1978), 3–14.; Farooq Aziz, “Interest (*ribā*) in Qur’anic perspective”, *European Journal of Social Sciences* 22/3 (2011), 338–41; Shahid Hasan Siddiqui, “*Ribā*, usury & interest –

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In its first appearance, Qur’ān 30: 39, dated in the third Meccan period,⁹ *ribā* is understood as the opposite activity to the payment of *zakāt*,¹⁰ but it is not directly prohibited, pointing to the fact that the prohibition of *ribā* has a mostly moral dimension:

“And what you give in usury, that it may increase upon the people’s wealth, increases not with God; but what you give in alms, desiring God’s Face, those – they receive recompense manifold.”

The ban of a specific activity appears in Qur’ān 3: 130, which, although it could refer to the practices performed in Mecca prior to the arrival of Islam, already belongs to the Medinan period:

“O believers, devour not usury, doubled and redoubled, and fear you God; haply so you will prosper.”

The restriction intensifies in the last of the four passages (Qur’ān 2: 275-281), and this time *ribā* is cast in opposition to trade, and not to *zakāt*, thus indicating a change in the perception of this issue:

“Those who devour usury shall not rise again except as he rises, whom Satan of the touch prostrates; that is because they say, ‘Trafficking (trade) is like usury.’ God has permitted trafficking, and forbidden usury. Whosoever receives an admonition from his Lord and gives over, he shall have his past gains, and his affair is committed to God; but whosoever reverts – those are the inhabitants of the Fire, therein dwelling forever. God blots out usury, but freewill offerings He augments with interest. God loves not any guilty ingrate. Those who believe and do deeds of righteousness, and perform the prayer, and pay the alms – their wage awaits them with their Lord, and no fear shall be on them, neither shall they sorrow. O believers, fear you God; and give up the usury that is outstanding, if you are believers. But if you do not, then take notice that God shall war with you, and His Messenger; yet if you repent, you shall have your principal, unwronging and wronged. And if any man should be in difficulties, let him have respite till things are easier; but that you should give freewill offerings is better for you, did you but know. And fear a day wherein you shall be returned to God, and every soul shall be paid in full what it has earned; and they shall not be wronged.”

In relation to the role played by non-Muslims in the Islamic doctrine of the prohibition of *ribā*, the only reference is related to the Jews of Medina (Qur’ān 4: 161).

historical and Qur’anic concept”, *Journal of Islamic Banking & Finance* 10/4 (1993), 43–7. I follow Arberry’s translation of the Qur’ān. Arthur J. Arberry, *The Koran* (Oxford: Oxford University, 1982).

⁸ Joseph Schacht, “Ribā”, *Encyclopaedia of Islam, Second Edition*, ed. Peri J. Bearman, Thierry Bianquis, Clifford Edmund Bosworth, Emeri J. van Donzel, Wolfhart P. Heinrichs. Consulted online on 11 May 2021 http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/1573-3912_islam_COM_0918.

⁹ Theodore Nöldeke, *Geschichte des Qorans* (Leipzig: T. Weicher, 1909-1938).

¹⁰ The term *zakāt* means “purification.” It is one of the five pillars of Islam and is prescribed in the *Qur’ān* and the *Sunna*. It consists of a mandatory donation collected by Muslim rulers which “purifies” the wealth from which the *zakāt* is taken. It is calculated on the basis of the individual’s assets. See Azim Nanji, “Almsgiving”, *Encyclopaedia of the Qur’an*, 5 vol., ed. Jane Dammen MacAuliffe (Leiden, Boston: Brill, 2006), I: 66–70.

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“... and for their taking usury, that they were prohibited, and consuming the wealth of the people in vanity; and We have prepared for the unbelievers among them a painful chastisement.”

This verse – discussed at length by specialists on the topic – could be read in light of the increasing tension in the relations between the Prophet and the Jews of Medina.¹¹ According to Joseph Schacht¹² and Montgomery Watt,¹³ for instance, the fact that the strictest passage against this practice belongs to the Medinan period indicates that at this point it became associated with the Jews of Medina, although what exactly it entailed is not described in the *sūra*. In any case, the ban on *ribā* was presented as a defining feature of Islamic moral standards which constituted a rupture with the prevailing practices all around, and therefore, in eyes of the Muslims, every non-Muslim was liable to practice *ribā*. In consequence, the accusation of usury found in the Qur’ān was addressed to the Jews because some of the inhabitants of Yathrib happened to be Jews, but it could have been similarly applied to Christians and pagans.

In fact, verses from the Meccan period frequently allude to the economic injustice that was prevalent in pagan Mecca at that time. Moreover, in the *Sunna* and the early jurisprudence, not only the Jews, but also the Christians are accused of practicing *ribā*. For example, the following *ḥadīth* refers to the (alleged) usurious activities of the people of Najrān,¹⁴ who were Christians:

*“The Messenger of Allah (blessings) concluded peace with the people of Najran on condition that they would pay to Muslims two thousand suits of garments, half in Safar, and the rest in Rajab, and they would lend (Muslims) thirty coats of mail, thirty horses, thirty camels, and thirty weapons of each type used in battle. Muslims will stand surely for them until they return them in case there is any plot or treachery in Yemen. No church of theirs will be demolished and no priest of theirs will be turned out. There will be no interruption in their religion unless they bring something new or take usury. Isma‘il said: They took usury.”*¹⁵

The Iraqi scholar Ibn Sa‘d (d. 230/845) wrote in his *Ṭabaqāt* that the caliph ‘Umar b. al-Khaṭṭāb expelled the Christians from the Arabian peninsula due to their usurious activities:¹⁶

وأقام أهل نجران على ما كتب لهم به النبي، حتى قبضه الله، صلوات الله عليه ورحمته ورضوانه وسلامه، ثم ولي أبو بكر الصديق فكتب بالوصاية بهم عند وفاته، ثم أصابوا ربا فأخرجهم عمر بن الخطاب من أرضهم.¹⁷

¹¹ For the general context see Michael Lecker, *Muslims, Jews and Pagans. Studies on Early Islamic Medina* (Piscataway: Gorgias Press, 2017).

¹² Schacht, “Ribā”, *IEP*.

¹³ Montgomery Watt, *Muhammad at Medina* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1956), 296–8.

¹⁴ Irfan Shahīd, “Najrān”, *IEP*. Consulted online on 19 May 2021 http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/1573-3912_islam_SIM_5729.

¹⁵ Abū Dā‘ūd, *Sunan - Jam‘ jawāmi‘ al-aḥādīth wa-al-asānīd wa-maknaz al-ṣiḥāḥ wa-al-sunan wa-al-masānīd* (Vaduz, Liechtenstein, Cairo: Jam‘iyyat al-maknaz al-islāmī (Thesaurus Islamicus Foundation), 2000-2001), [3043], 528.

¹⁶ Gordon Nickel, “‘We Will Make Peace With You’. The Christians of Najrān in Muqātil’s *Tafsīr*”, *Collectanea Christiana Orientalia* 3 (2006), 171–88, 182. He refers to Ibn Sa‘d, *al-Ṭabaqāt al-Kubrā* (Beirut: Dār Ṣādir, 1957), I: 358.

¹⁷ Ibn Sa‘d, *al-Ṭabaqāt al-Kubrā*, ed. ‘Alī Muḥammad ‘Umar (Cairo: Maktabat al-Khanjī, 2001), I: 308.

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*And the people of Najran complied with what the Prophet had established for them, until God seized him, may God’s blessings, mercy, pleasure and peace be upon him. Then, Abū Bakr al-Ṣiddīq ruled and wrote down the prescriptions related to them when he (the Prophet) died. Then they (the people from Najrān) practiced ribā and ‘Umar b. al-Khaṭṭāb expelled them from their lands.*¹⁸

Coming back to the Qur’ān, it is in the Medinan verses where the term *ribā* was applied to specific activities that, unfortunately, are not fully described. We can only infer that the practices mentioned in Qur’ān 4: 161 performed by Jews were related to loans – and not to trade – in which the two- and four-fold profits were exacted, and that the same practice was attributed to the Christians in the above-mentioned hadith. Although in the eyes of the Muslims the ban on *ribā* was a defining feature of Islamic moral standards as opposed to the immoral practices of Jews and Christians, as in Judaism and Christianity some Muslim legal scholars such as Ḥanafī jurist al-Shaybānī (d. 189/805)¹⁹ later argued that both Muslims and *dhimmī*-s could perform usurious transactions when they were outside Muslim territory (*Dār al-Islām*). Some jurists, such as al-Kāsānī (d. 587/1189), even allowed for usurious transactions between Muslims, as long as they took place outside *Dār al-Islām*.²⁰

The credit needs of the different Muslim populations propitiated the emergence of interest-concealing transactions which could meet such needs without formally breaking the law.²¹ Although there was a parallel process in Judaism and Christianity,²² in the Islamic context no type of *ribā* was openly legalised while, for instance, in Latin-Christian context, the practices of financial institutions related to the Church, such as the *arcas de misericordia* and the *montes pietatis*, were considered as a legal kind of interest-bearing loans.²³ Instead, we find in Islamic jurisprudence individual dissenting opinions as to the validity of interest-concealing activities and about exactly what was

¹⁸ This made me wonder whether the practice of *ribā* could have been also adduced as one of the arguments to justify the actions against the Jews from Yathrib. However, Michael Lecker’s impression is that the apologetics justifying the expulsion and massacre of the Jews of Medina in the biography of the Prophet are mostly focused on military, political and theological themes. I would like to thank him his willingness to help me with this issue.

¹⁹ Al-Shaybānī, *Sharḥ kitāb al-siyar al-kabīr* (Cairo: Ma’had al-makhtūṭāt bi-jāmi‘at al-duwal al-‘arabiyya, 1971-1972), IV: 1486–8.

²⁰ Khaled Abou el Fadl, “Islamic Law and Muslim Minorities. The Juristic Discourse on Muslim Minorities from the Second/Eighth to the Seventh/Eleventh Centuries”, *Islamic Law and Society* 1 (1994), 141–87, 141, 174. He refers to al-Kāsānī, *Badā’i’ al-Ṣanā’i’* (Beirut: Dār al-kutub al-‘ilmiyya, 1986), VII: 132.

²¹ Adday Hernández, *El valor del tiempo. Doctrina jurídica y práctica de la usura (ribā) en el Occidente islámico medieval* [Humaniora, 376] (Helsinki: Academia Scientiarum Fennica, 2016).

²² Cornell mentions some specific contracts that were permitted by the Church: *Feuda; Fide-jussor; Pro dote; Stipenda clerici; Venditio fructus; Cui velle juri nocer; Vendens sub dubio; Pretium post tempora solvens; Poena nec in fraudem* (or *poena conventionalis*); *Lex commisoria; Gratis dans; Socii pompa* and *Labor*. Cornell, “In the Shadow”, 20. Likewise, in Judaism, Maimonides dealt with the “shadows of usury” in reference to those activities that conceal the interest-taking, Baron, “The economic views”, 214–6.

²³ Javier Castaño, “Crédito caritativo en la Castilla de mediados del siglo XV. Los estatutos de las «Arcas de la Misericordia» y la «usura» judía”, *Prestare ai Poveri. Il credito su pegno e il Monte di Pietà in area Mediterranea (secoli XV-XIX)*, (Bologna: Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Istituto di Studi sulle Società del Mediterraneo, 2007), 101–43; Maria Giuseppina Muzzarelli, *Il denaro e la salvezza. L’invenzione del Monte di Pietà* (Bologna: Il Mulino, 2001); “Candelabrum Lucem Ferens. Il prestito del monte di pietà nel pensiero dei giuristi Benedetto Capra e Baglione dei Montevidiani”, *Credito e usura fra teologia, diritto e amministrazione. Linguaggi a confronto (SEC. XII-XIV)*, ed. Diego Quaglioni, Giacomo Todeschini, Gian Maria Varanini [Collection de l’Ecole Française de Rome, 346] (Rome: École Française de Rome, 2005), 181–96.

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to be considered *ribā*. Loans were usually performed by individual money-lenders and they used to consist in small amounts to be returned after short terms without being framed within any kind of financial institution.²⁴ This could be due to the extant tension in Islamic societies between a hierarchical and secular political power and the non-hierarchical religious power. As described by Eduardo Manzano and Susana Narotzky, the different development of economic institutions might have to do with the divergences between the internal organisation of the Islamic religious community (*umma*) as opposed to its Christian counterpart (*ekklesia*). While the later became a hierarchical organisation, the former did not contemplate, in principle, the existence of privileged groups or elites.²⁵

Regarding the traditions of the *Salaf* generation (*aḥādīth* and *akhbār*)²⁶ on this topic, several references can be found in a legal question (*mas’ala*) issued by the Naṣrid jurist al-Shāṭibī (d. 790/1388), to which I will return later. In it, al-Shāṭibī quotes several of these traditions with the aim of demonstrating that, in spite of the unlawful activities performed by the *dhimmī*-s (meaning both Christians and Jews, not Jews specifically), the *Salaf* generation permitted Muslims to eat their food, take the *jizya* tax from them, and accept their gifts and donations unless something illegal about them was discovered (and proven with irrefutable evidence). The traditions he quotes, however, do not mention the religion of those who practice *ribā* and it seems that al-Shāṭibī himself interpreted them as referring to non-Muslims.²⁷

قال لعمر ابن الخطاب رضى الله عنه: ’ما جاءها²⁸ من هذا المال والتغير مشرف ولا سائل فخذة وما لا فلا تتبعه نفسك‘.

‘Umar b. al-Khaṭṭāb: “What comes to you of this kind of money without having looked for it, take it, and what does not come, don’t let your soul be eager for it”.

فعن ابن مسعود انه قيل له ان في جار الا يتورع من اكل الربى ولا من اخذ ما لا يصلح وهو يدعوننا الى طعامه وتكون لنا الحاجة فنستقرضه فقال: ’اذا دعاك الى طعامه فاجبه فاذا كانت لك حاجة فاستقرضه فان اثمه لموليه ومهناه لك‘.

²⁴ According to Timur Kuran, this lack of institutionalisation of credit activities partially motivated economic stagnation in Muslim countries: Timur Kuran, *The Long Divergence: How Islamic law held back the Middle East* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2011), 13.

²⁵ Eduardo Manzano; Susana Narotzky, “The Hisba, the Muhtasib and the Struggle over Political Power and a Moral Economy. An Enquiry into Institutions”, *Diverging Paths? The Shapes of Power and Institutions in Medieval Christendom and Islam*, ed. John Hudson and Ana Rodríguez (Leiden: Brill, 2014), 30–54, 37.

²⁶ The *akhbār* are reports or narratives that are not attributed to the Prophet Muḥammad (as in the case of the *aḥādīth*), but to his Companions (*ṣaḥāba*) or followers (*ṭābi‘ūn*). See James Robson, “Hadīth”, *EP*. Consulted online on 03 November 2020 http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/1573-3912_islam_COM_0248.

²⁷ It is not clear whether al-Shāṭibī thought that these traditions were exclusively referring to the illicit goods coming from non-Muslims. But as the acceptance of the non-Muslims’ food and the collection of the *jizya* tax from them constitutes the basis of al-Shāṭibī’s argumentation, it is clear that he considered *dhimmī*-s as the most likely group to possess unlawful goods, some of which could have been obtained through the practice of *ribā*, as mentioned in the text. Abū Ishāq al-Shāṭibī (d. 790/1388), *Mu‘āmalat man istaghraqa fī dhimmatihī al-ḥarām* (MS 362/3, Casablanca: King Abdul Aziz Foundation), first section, fol. 1r–1v. I am currently editing and translating this text in my forthcoming monograph *Dealing with corruption in Naṣrid Granada. Abū Ishāq al-Shāṭibī (d. 790/1388) Mu‘āmalat man istaghraqa fī dhimmatihī al-ḥarām*.

²⁸ It should read “جاءك”.

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Ibn Mas‘ūd [narrated] that he was told about a neighbour: “*He refrains neither from consuming usury [ribā] nor from taking what is not right [lā yaṣlah]. He offers us his food and we borrow from him when we are in need*”. He said: “*If he offers you his food, accept it, and if you are in need, borrow from him, since the sin is on the one who commits it, and for you it is a [mere] benefit*”.

وسئل ابن عمر فقيل له ان في جارا يأكل الربى وانه يدعوني الى طعامه. افاتيه؟ قال: “نعم”.

Ibn ‘Umar was asked about a neighbor who habitually practiced usury: “*He offers me his food; shall I accept it?*” He said: “*Yes*”.

وسئل النخعي عن الرجل يرث المال منه الحلال والحرام قال: “لا يحرم عليه الا حرام بعينه”. وقال: “من

اذا ورث مالا حراما وحلالا فلم يعلم الحلال من الحرام لم يحرم عليه حتى يعلم الحلال من الحرام”.

Al-Nakha‘ī was asked about a man who inherited some goods, part of them lawful and the other unlawful, and he said: “*Only what is specifically banned is prohibited*”. And he said: “*If someone inherited lawful and unlawful goods and it is not known which goods are lawful and which are not, [the inheritance] is not forbidden until the nature of each good is determined*”.

وعن سعيد بن جبير انه مر بالعشارين في ايديهم شماريخ فقال: “ناولني²⁹ من سحتكم هذا انه عليكم حرام ولنا حلال”.

Sa‘īd b. Jubayr (on tax collectors): “*Offer me your illicit profit, since it is prohibited for you, but for us it is lawful*”.³⁰

وسئل ابن ابي نئب عن اعطي من مال قد علم ان شيء حلال و حراما لها انه قد اختلط، “يقبله؟” قال: “نعم. ما لم يعلم انه حرام بعمليه”.

Ibn Abī Dhi’b was asked about someone who was given some goods known to be a mixture of lawful and unlawful, “*Shall I accept it?*” He said: “*Yes. If the unlawfulness as to how it was obtained is not known*”.

The prohibition of usury in Judaism and Christianity³¹

The ban on interest in the Bible and in later texts is based on two fundamental points:³²

- The rich must help the poor, either through donations and gifts, or through interest-free loans. This idea is similar to that found in Qur’ān 30: 39, where *ribā* is described as the opposite of *zakāt*.
- Collecting excessive interest is the basis for social ruin and, therefore, interest should be prohibited in general. In Ezequiel (22:12, 15-16), usury is referred to

²⁹ In some versions of this *ḥadīth* I have found “ناولونا”.

³⁰ This tradition means that the unlawful gain is only illicit for those who commit the illegal act, while the unlawfulness is not applicable to the one who receives it as a gift or a donation. Tax collectors are often seen as guilty of taking unlawful gain when they collect taxes on behalf of the ruler which are not prescribed by the main sources of Islamic law.

³¹ I would like to thank Laura Righi, Anna Mambelli and Professor Alberto Melloni for their suggestions regarding this section. What follows is merely aimed at providing a general overview of the Jewish and Christian contexts.

³² Eliash Ben-Zion, “Usury”, *Encyclopaedia Judaica*, (New York: Macmillan, 2007), XX: 437–43.

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as an activity that should be punished, and God says that his people must be dispersed throughout different foreign regions as punishment for their sins, among them usury.

There are several references to usury as evil in the Torah, one example of which is Leviticus 25:35-37:

“And if thy brother be waxen poor, and his means fail with thee; then thou shalt uphold him: as a stranger and a settler shall he live with thee. Take thou no interest of him or increase; but fear thy God; that thy brother may live with thee. Thou shalt not give him thy money upon interest, nor give him thy victuals for increase”.³³

On the other hand, in Deuteronomy 23:20 we find:

“Unto a foreigner thou mayest lend upon interest; but unto thy brother thou shalt not lend upon interest”.³⁴

According to Vincent Cornell, the passage found in Deuteronomy uses the term *neshekh* to refer to usury, which literally means "bite." The passage in Leviticus, on the other hand, uses, in addition to this term, that of *tarbit*, and the terms *ribbit* and *marbit*, derived from the same stem, also appear in other places.³⁵

The rabbinic discussions related to usury contained in the Talmud constitute the basis of the Jewish jurisprudence on this issue. In this rabbinic literature, usury seems to be identified with any kind of interest. This concept was called "dust of interest" or *avak ribbit*, which became the main subject of discussions on usury in the *Mishnah* and other later commentaries. In these works, the lawfulness of specific activities was analysed in the light of these juridical discussions, as well as the meaning of the different terms appearing in the main sources.³⁶ However, the specialists in Talmud do not agree on the connotations of each of them.³⁷

The issue of interest-bearing loans to Gentiles is dealt with in the Talmud, but no definite conclusion was drawn from that debate, so in the post-Talmudic period the

³³ The quotations from the Hebrew Bible are taken from *Mechon Mamre: A Hebrew - English Bible. According to the Masoretic Text and the JPS 1917 Edition*. <https://www.mechon-mamre.org/p/pt/pt0.htm> Consulted on 22 August 2020.

³⁴ There is a third reference in the Pentateuch to the prohibition of interests: Exodus 22:24. For more information on the exegesis of these three passages and the change in the terminology employed in each of them see John Van Seters, *A Law Book for the Diaspora: Revision in the Study of the Covenant Code* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2002), 132–3; Hillel Gamoran "The Biblical Law against Loans on Interest", *Journal of Near Eastern Studies* 30/2 (1971), 127–34; *Jewish Law in Transition. How Economic Forces Overcame the Prohibition against Lending on Interest* (Cincinnati: Hebrew Union College Press, 2008).

³⁵ Cornell, "In the Shadow of Deuteronomy", 13–4.

³⁶ "Baba Meziah", *The Babylonian Talmud. Mishná, séder Nizikin*, ed. Rabi Dr. I. Epstein (London: The Soncino Press, 1935) II, 5:1; 5:2; 5:7.

³⁷ For the Andalusī Maimonides, *neshekh* refers to the cumulative interest, while *tarbit* is used to refer to fixed interest. However in his work *Mishne Torah*, both terms appear as synonyms. In the Jewish Publication Society's translation of Leviticus, *neshekh* is considered as the interest discounted prior to the transaction, while *tarbit* is translated as "accrued interest" that is charged at the moment of the payment, the opposite interpretation of Maimonides'. In the *Mishnah*, *neshekh* was described as the interest earned in a monetary transaction, while the term *tarbit* referred to the increase of the commodity in a loan. See Cornell, "In the Shadow of Deuteronomy", 14; Maimonides, *Mishné Torá* (Tel Aviv: El árbol de la vida, 1982), II: 283.

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discussion continued. Halachic discussions have also dealt with the issue, especially in terms of specific aspects, such as cases in which the Gentile is an apostate from Judaism.³⁸

Regarding Christianity, Jones, in his work on the reform of the morality of usury in Christianity,³⁹ states that the pillars on which the ecclesiastical prohibition of usury was based were three: the prohibition of usury in the Holy Scriptures, the philosophical and the historical approaches. Scriptural arguments first took shape in Hebrew culture. Philosophical arguments, on the other hand, have their origin in Greek and Roman thinkers, while historical ones are the result of the thought of the first Church Fathers.

The Old Testament coincides with the Hebrew Bible, but some scholars have argued that the reticence against charging interest was stronger among Christians, and that this is reflected in the change of the terminology employed and the universalisation of the concept of brotherhood.⁴⁰ While little is said about usury in the New Testament, early Christians adopted the Graeco-Roman philosophical arguments against usury, according to which usury was “*an unnatural means of acquiring money*”⁴¹ and the first Church Fathers, influenced by the classical arguments of Plato and Aristotle, strongly disapproved of charging interest on loans.⁴²

The practice of usury is closely linked to the figure of Judas Iscariot and simony, a heresy consisting of the sale of the spiritual through material goods. This is because usury is one of the activities that most clearly reflects the search for an immediate material reward, which is what Judas was looking for when he sold Christ for thirty pieces of silver. This type of mentality is defined by Christian scholasticism as a commercial incapacity or economic irrationality, since it prevents the one who has it from seeing the benefits of spiritual rewards.⁴³

Usury was prohibited in various councils of the Church such as that of Elvira in 305 or 306, the council of Arles in 314 and the first council of Nicaea in 325, in the

³⁸ Daniel Breslauer, *Toward a Jewish (M)Orality. Speaking of a postmodern Jewish ethics* (Westport, London: Greenwood Press, 1998), 147. He refers to Ezra Basri, *The Laws of Interest*, 178–96.

³⁹ Jones, *Reforming the Morality of Usury*, 18.

⁴⁰ Paul Mills, *Interest in Interest. The Old Testament Ban on Interest and its Applications for Today* (Cambridge: Jubilee Centre, 1989), 8–9.

⁴¹ According to Maloney, Plato, like Aristotle, saw money as barren, so it could not create more money. According to him, Plato wrote that “*the amassing of wealth was incompatible with sober and virtuous citizenship*.” He also stated that greed reduced many to poverty and that it created debtors who were eager for revolution. Robert P. Maloney, “Usury in Greek, Roman and Rabbinic Thought”, *Traditio* 27 (1971), 79–109, 81, 86–7.

⁴² Terence P. McLaughlin, “The Teaching of the Canonists on Usury”, *Mediaeval Studies* 1 (1939), 81–147 and 2 (1940), 1–22; John T. Noonan, *The Scholastic Analysis of Usury* (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1957); Robert P. Maloney, “The Teaching of the Fathers on Usury. An Historical Study on the Development of Christian Thinking”, *Vigiliae Christianae* 27 (1973), 241–65, 264–5.

⁴³ Giacomo Todeschini has detected this association already in the texts of early Christian exegetes such as Saint Ambrose of Milan and other patristic writings. See Giacomo Todeschini, “Christian Perceptions of Jewish Economic Activity in the Middle Ages”, *Wirtschaftsgeschichte der mittelalterlichen Juden. Fragen und Einschätzungen*, ed. Michael Toch (Munich: De Gruyter Oldenbourg, 2008), 1–16, 7–8; *Come Giuda. La gente comune e i giochi dell'economia all'inizio dell'epoca moderna* (Bologna: Il Mulino, 2011). He refers to Bernhard Blumenkranz, *Die Judenpredigt Augustins. Ein Beitrag zur Geschichte der jüdisch-christlichen Beziehungen in den ersten Jahrhunderten* (Basel: Helbing & Lichtenhahn, 1946); *Les auteurs chrétiens latins du Moyen Âge sur les Juifs et le Judaïsme* (Paris: Mouton, 1963); Heinz Schreckenberg, *Die christliche Adversus Judaeos-Texte und ihr literarisches und historisches Umfeld (I–XI Jh.)* (Frankfurt, Bern, etc.: Lang, 1982); Miriam S. Taylor, *Anti-Judaism and Early Christian Identity. A Critique of the Scholarly Consensus* (Leiden: Brill, 1995).

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seventeenth canon. Later councils emulated the prohibition of usury that emerged from the first council of Nicaea, such as the first council of Carthage (348), whose prohibition was reaffirmed in the third (397), fourth (398) and sixth (401) councils, and that of Laodicea (364).⁴⁴ In the fifth century, Pope Leo I the Great wrote the epistle *Nec hoc quoque*, a papal decree that categorically forbade churchmen to practice usury, but also proclaimed that those laymen who sought reprehensible profit were also guilty. This epistle is included in the *Hadriana*, the most influential body of ecclesiastical legislation for the Empire of Charlemagne (800-814).

Usury – in reference to profits obtained from monetary loans – was only prohibited to Christians after 800 AD, when decrees issued in the provincial councils of the Latin Church extended the prohibition beyond clerics, making it applicable to the lay population. Both the Church and the various rulers intensified the fight against usury in this moment. Opinions diversified as time passed and, among the different Church authorities, there were many who suggested the possibility of charging interests in transactions with the enemies. They argued, to justify their position, that also killing was forbidden, but that, in the event of war, killing was practiced in order to achieve a greater good. These opinions coexisted with those of absolute condemnation of any activity involving the charging of interests, including speculating with food and raising its price in times of famine.

The first Christian theologians, such as Saint Ambrose of Milan (d. 397), dismissed the idea that lending to non-Christians was permitted when it implied a personal benefit.⁴⁵ However, with the passing of time, this idea eventually took hold, and it became licit to practice usury against Jews and Muslims because they were “*enemies of Christ*”.⁴⁶ Rabanus Maurus (d. 856) and, several centuries later, Bernardus Papiensis (d. 1213), among others, also confirmed the legality of charging Muslims interest, while Huguccio of Pisa (d. 1188), in his *Summa decretorum*, and John of Wildeshausen (d. 1252) or *Johannes Teutonicus* legitimised usury against enemies – whether Muslims, pagans, Jews, heretics, or even other Christians – when at war with them.⁴⁷

During the Crusades, both Muslims and Christians identified elements in the religion of the Other to fight against, thus highlighting the positive aspects of their own doctrines. In particular, this period was decisive regarding the attitude that the Catholic Church would take regarding loans at interest. Pope Eugene III, who in 1146 made the call to the Crusade, issued a bull by virtue of which those who took part in the enterprise would be freed from their debts. He also proclaimed a moratorium on the interests that

⁴⁴ Jones, *Reforming the Morality of Usury*, 31.

⁴⁵ Saint Ambrose stated that a Christian might exact usury from one whom he may justly harm, which was then interpreted as an indiscriminate exaction of usury from Jews, pagans, and heretics – the enemies of the medieval Church. However, he did not intend this statement as permission to collect interest with no restrictions, but only as a mechanism for recovering properties unjustly held by non-Christians. See John A. Lorenc, *John of Freiburg and the Usury Prohibition in the Late Middle Ages. A Study in the Popularization of Medieval Canon Law*, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Toronto, 2013, 89, n. 63.

⁴⁶ Cornell, “In the Shadow of Deuteronomy”, 19.

⁴⁷ Cornell, “In the Shadow of Deuteronomy”, 19. Reference to *Johannes Teutonicus* might be derived from a misattribution of the *Summa confessorum* on usury to this author, more recently attributed to the Franciscan John of Freiburg (d. 1314). See John A. Lorenc, *John of Freiburg and the Usury Prohibition*, 11–2.

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the crusaders owed. In this context, there was a renewed interest in the debate on usury in the Catholic Church. Since, in the eyes of some Popes, especially Innocent III, the success of the Crusades required that the activities of money-lenders – both Jewish and Christian, and both religious and secular – be restricted, the intention was, albeit unsuccessfully, to apply the prohibition of usury to everyone living in Christian territories.⁴⁸ At the same time, coinciding with the economic and commercial revolution that took place around the twelfth century, some types of interest were legalised.⁴⁹ Thus, in Christian contexts, usury came to refer to a specific form of interest-bearing credit that individuals issued for their own benefit, as demonstrated by some of the texts conforming the anti-usurious policy of the thirteenth century, such as the *Decretals* of Pope Gregory IX (1227-1241).⁵⁰

Regarding the association of the Jews with the usurious money loans, around this time, Saint Bernard of Clairvaux (d. 1153) employed for the first time the term “*to Judaize*” to refer to usurious practices, and suggested that Christian money-lenders should be disdainfully referred to as “*baptised Jews*”.⁵¹ During the fourth Lateran council (1215) the most restrictive rules to date against the loans performed by Jews were issued.⁵²

The creation of the *montes pietatis*,⁵³ an institution through which the Church charged legally sanctioned interest on loans, responded to the Franciscan idea that the institutionalisation of credit-related activities would contribute to public growth and welfare.⁵⁴ The assumption was that their loans would pay back into the benefit of the community, while loans given by Jews (or analogous money-lenders) would only contribute to the lender’s own personal profit. It can be said, therefore, that they based their acceptance of a certain kind of interest on the concept of the common good. This opposition between legal and illegal interests reflected the division established in the Christian context between those who considered economic matters in allegorical or spiritual terms, and those who did in material terms, represented by Judas. The association between the figure of Judas and the Jews established centuries earlier by the Fathers of the Latin Church further contributed to the formation of the stereotype of the Jewish usurer.⁵⁵

⁴⁸ Benjamin Nelson, *The idea of Usury. From tribal brotherhood to Universal Otherhood* (Chicago, London: University of Chicago Press, 1969), 3–28, 7.

⁴⁹ See, for instance, Robert Sabatino Lopez, *The Commercial Revolution of the Middle Ages, 950-1350* (London: 1976); Avner Greif, “On the Political Foundations of the Late Medieval Commercial Revolution: Genoa During the Twelfth and Thirteenth Centuries”, *The Journal of Economic History* 54/2 (1994), 271–87.

⁵⁰ Gregorio IX, *Decretales de Gregorio IX. Versión medieval española*, ed. Jaime M. Mans Puigarnau (Barcelona: Universidad de Barcelona. Facultad de Derecho, 1939-1942), Titulus XIX, De Usuris, C. XII; C. XV; C. XVIII.

⁵¹ Fernando Suárez Bilbao, “Los judíos y las Cruzadas. Las consecuencias y su situación jurídica” (Introducción), *Medievalismo: Boletín de la Sociedad Española de Estudios Medievales* 6 (1996), 121–46, 143.

⁵² Robert Chazan, *European Jewry and the First Crusade* (California: University of California Press, 1996), 181.

⁵³ They became widespread in the second half of the fifteenth century in central and northern Italy at the initiative of the Franciscans, although the Italian city-states had already had them since the twelfth century. See Muzzarelli, *Il denaro e la salvezza*; “Candelabrum Lucem Ferens”.

⁵⁴ On the economic doctrine of the Franciscans see Giacomo Todeschini, *Ricchezza francescana. Dalla povertà volontaria alla società di mercato* (Bologna: Il Mulino, 2004).

⁵⁵ Todeschini, “Christian Perceptions”, 7–8; see also Todeschini, *La banca e il ghetto. Una storia italiana (secoli XIV-XVI)* (Roma-Bari: Laterza, 2016).

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If we move the focus from religious texts to the actual practice on the ground, a variety of situations and responses can be ascertained on which there is a rich bibliography.⁵⁶

Mālikī legal texts referring to Christians and Jews practicing ribā

Moving now to al-Andalus, historical sources and polemical literature against religions other than Islam, such as Ibn Ḥazm’s works (*al-Fiṣal fī-al-milal wa-al-ahwā’ wa-al-niḥal* and *Radd Abī Muḥammad b. Ḥazm ‘alā Ibn al-Naghriḥa al-yahūdī*), among others, have been consulted, but it is exclusively in legal sources that I have been able to find examples connecting *ribā* with non-Muslims. Such legal sources include normative and theoretical works, *ḥisba* treatises dealing with the inspection of what takes place in the market⁵⁷ and, finally, works on casuistry (*masā’il* and *fatāwā*) that shed light on the relation between theory and practice.⁵⁸

In al-Andalus and more generally in the Islamic West, the Mālikī school of law was prevalent. In one of the main foundational texts, Saḥnūn’s *Mudawwana*,⁵⁹ Mālik is said to have reported that ‘Umar b. al-Khaṭṭāb forbade Jews and Christians to act as money-changers or butchers in Muslim markets:

قال مالك وبلغني أن عمر بن الخطاب كتب الى البلدان نيهامهم أن يكون النصرارى واليهود في أسواقهم
صيافة أو جزارين وأن يقاموا من الاسواق كلها فان الله قد أغنانا بالمسلمين.

Mālik said: “*I was told that ‘Umar b. al-Khaṭṭāb wrote to [all] the [Muslim] countries and forbade them from letting Christians and Jews act as money-changers or butchers and stay in their markets, since God has provided us with Muslims*”.

The reference to money-changers in this text has to do with the fact that the fundamental basis of the Islamic jurisprudence on *ribā* is the *hadīth* of ‘the six commodities’ that regulates the exchange of gold, silver, wheat, barley, dates and salt. Several versions are included in all the canonical hadith collections.⁶⁰ Some of them

⁵⁶ From some contributions we can infer that, in spite of the undeniable existence of the stereotype of the Jewish usurer, people were also aware of the need and legitimacy of the interest-bearing loans. See, for instance, Maya Soifer-Irish, “The Problem of Old Debts. Jewish Money-lenders in Northern Castile”, *Sefarad* 74:2 (2014), 279–302; Joseph Shatzmiller, *Shylock Reconsidered. Jews, Moneylending, and Medieval Society* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1990); William Jordan, “Jews on Top. Women and the Availability of Consumption Loans in Northern France in the Mid-Thirteenth Century”, *Journal of Jewish Studies* 29 (1978), 39–56; David Nirenberg, *Communities of Violence. Persecution of Minorities in the Middle Ages* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1996), 30–40; Claude Denjean, *La loi du lucre. L’usure en procès dans la Couronne d’Aragon à la fin du Moyen Âge* (Madrid: Casa de Velazquez, 2011); Stephen P. Besch, *Barcelona and its rulers 1096-1291* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1995), 284; Elka Klein, *Jews, Christian Society and Royal Power in medieval Barcelona* (Michigan: Ann Arbor, University of Michigan Press, 2006), 162; Anna Sapir Abulafia, *Christian-Jewish Relations, 1000-1300. Jews in the service of Medieval Christendom* (London: Routledge, 2014).

⁵⁷ The *ḥisba* treatises deal with the activities and frauds that should be controlled by the inspector (*muhtasib*) in the market, and also with moral issues such as the avoidance of the practice of *ribā*. See Manzano and Narotzky, “The *Hisba*, the *Muhtasib*”, 39.

⁵⁸ David Powers, *Law, Society and Culture in the Maghrib, 1300-1500* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2002), 7–8; 229–33.

⁵⁹ Saḥnūn b. Sa‘īd al-Tanūkhī, *al-Mudawwana al-kubrā* (Cairo: Maṭba‘at al-Sa‘āda, 1905), III: 67–8.

⁶⁰ Al-Bukhārī, *Ṣaḥīḥ - Jam‘ jawāmi‘ al-aḥādīth wa-al-asānīd wa-maknaz al-ṣiḥāḥ wa-al-sunan wa-al-masānīd* (Vaduz, Liechtenstein, Cairo: Jam‘iyyat al-maknaz al-islāmī (Thesaurus Islamicus Foundation), 2000-2001), [2210], 403; Ibn Māja, *Sunan*, [2338], 326; Abū Dā‘ūd, *Sunan*, [3350], 578; al-Nasā‘ī, *Sunan - Jam‘ jawāmi‘ al-aḥādīth wa-*

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focus on the exchange of gold and silver, which placed *ṣarf* (exchange of money and precious metals) among the legally dubious activities:⁶¹

حدثنا ثبید الرحمن بن أبی بكرة قال قال أبو بكرة قال رسول الله لا تتبعوا الذهب بالذهب إلا سواء بسواء والفضة بالفضة لا سواء بسواء وبيعوا الذهب بالفضة والفضة بالذهب كيف شئتم.

“We were told that ‘Abd al-Raḥmān b. Abī Bakra said: Abū Bakra reported that the Prophet (blessings) said: Do not sell gold for gold, except in the same amount nor silver for silver except in the same amount. Sell gold for silver and silver for gold as you want.”

In al-Andalus, the Andalusī jurist ‘Abd al-Malik b. Ḥabīb (d. 238/852) accused money-changers of assiduously practicing *ribā*.⁶²

قال وحدثني مطرف بن عبد الله عن مالك بن أنس قال: وكان الحسن يقول: “إن استقيت ماء فسقيته من بيت الصراف فلا تشربه.”

قال عبد المالك بن حبيب: “لأن الغالب عليهم عمل الربا وقد قال رسول الله صلى الله عليه وسلم: لعن الله آكل الربا وموكله.”

I was told by Muṭarrif b. ‘Abd Allāh, who took it from Mālik b. Anas, that he said: “Al-Ḥasan [al-Baṣrī] said: ‘If someone serves you water in a money-changer’s house, do not drink it’. ‘Abd al-Malik b. Ḥabīb said: ‘Because most of them practice *ribā* and the Prophet (blessings) said: “God curses *ribā* and those who consume it”’.

In his *ḥisba* treatise, entitled *Risāla fī ādāb al-ḥisba wa-al-muḥtasib*, Ibn ‘Abd al-Ra’ūf (fourth/tenth century) refers to Ibn Ḥabīb, and associates *ṣarf* and *ribā* with *dhimmī*-s.⁶³ He adds that money-changers often obtain illegal benefits from the exchange of gold and silver. Like ‘Umar b. al-Khaṭṭāb, he thinks that the usurious practices performed by the money-changers could be avoided if *dhimmī*-s and other dubious persons were not allowed to practice *ṣarf*, as in the following passage on exerting control over sales (*al-naẓar fī al-buyū*):⁶⁴

”ومرجعها إلى أهل الصرف في الغالب. فمن النظر في ذلك أن لا يستعمل فيه نذميا ولا متهما في كسبه. ونهى الحسن أن يشرب الماء من بيت الصراف.“ قال ابن حبيب: “لأن الغالب عليه عمل الربى.”

al-asānīd wa-maknaz al-ṣiḥāh wa-al-sunan wa-al-masānīd (Vaduz, Liechtenstein, Cairo: Jam‘iyyat al-maknaz al-islāmī (Thesaurus Islamicus Foundation), 2000-2001), [4575], 742.

⁶¹ Al-Bukhārī, *Ṣaḥīḥ*, [2215], 403. Ibn Māja even included a tradition in which the Prophet is said to have banned *ṣarf*. See Ibn Māja, *Sunan*, [2343], 327.

⁶² ‘Abd al-Malik b. Ḥabīb, *Kitāb al-ribā*, ed. Nadir Ouahab (Dubai: Markaz Jum‘a al-Mājid li-al-thaqāfa wa-al-turāth (Juma Almajid Center for Culture and Heritage), 2012), 58. Spanish translation in Adday Hernández, *El Kitāb al-ribā de ‘Abd al-Malik b. Ḥabīb (m. 238/852): La doctrina legal temprana sobre la usura* [Fuentes Árabe-hispanas 37] (Madrid: CSIC, 2017), 29.

⁶³ Ibn Ḥabīb, however, did not mention *dhimmī*-s.

⁶⁴ *Thalāth rasā’il andalusīyya fī ādāb al-ḥisba wa-l-muḥtasib. Trois traités hispaniques de ḥisba*, ed. Évariste Lévi-Provençal (Cairo: Maṭba‘at al-Ma‘had al-‘ilmī al-Faransī li-al-athār al-Sharqiyya, 1955), 84. French translation in Rachel Arié, “Traduction annotée et commentée des traités de *ḥisba* d’Ibn ‘Abd al-Ra’ūf et de ‘Umar al-Ġarsifī”, *Hesperis Tamuda* 1 (1960), 5–38; 199-214; 349–86, 34. New edition and Spanish translation in Pedro Chalmeta, Ibn ‘Abd al-Ra’ūf. *Córdoba a mediados del siglo X* (Almería: Fundación Ibn Tufayl de Estudios Árabes, 2019) 31, [13]; trans. 68–9.

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“Control over this activity implies ensuring that it is not carried out with a dhimmī or a person whose assets have a dubious origin. Al-Ḥasan [al-Baṣrī] forbade drinking water in the money changer’s house”. Ibn Ḥabīb said: “Because most of them practice ribā”.

On the contrary, the regulation of the exchange of money and precious metals is not at the core of the Christian doctrine on usury as far as I have been able to observe, so that it can be considered as one of the distinctive aspects of the two approaches.

For the period of the Cordoban Umayyad emirate and caliphate (ninth-tenth centuries CE), there is another reference alluding to the dhimmī-s, thus encompassing both Christians and Jews. It is a passage from the *‘Utbiyya*, a legal text composed in the third/ninth century CE:⁶⁵

قالت: “فهل لحكم المسلمين أن يقضي بين أهل الذمة فيما يتظلمون فيه من الأموال أو من البيوع والرهن والغصب؟” فقال: “نعم، ذلك الذي يحق عليه”، قلت: “ففي أي شيء يترك الحكم بينهم؟” قال “في حدودهم وعتقهم وطلاقهم وبيع الربا التي يتبايعون بها من الدرهم بالدرهمين ونحو هذا ونكاحهم”.

I [‘Īsā b. Dinār] said: “Should the arbitrator [ḥakām] of the Muslims be the one to judge among the people of the dhimma the conflicts that may arise between them over property, or questions of sales or garments or usurpation of property?”

Ibn al-Qāsim] replied: “Yes, he is entitled to this”.

I [‘Īsā b. Dinār] said: “And what does the ḥakām not judge among them?”

Ibn al-Qāsim] replied: “He does not judge in their criminal disputes [ḥudūd], their manumissions, their divorces, the sales with **usury** they carry out in their business transactions, of one dirham in exchange for two and the like, and their marriage contracts”.⁶⁶

In the two early texts of Ibn ‘Abd al-Ra’ūf and al-‘Utbī, what we find is an association between *ribā* and non-Muslims, not specifically or exclusively with Jews. According to scholars such as Mark Cohen, the situation of the Jews under Muslim rule was slightly better than in Christian lands,⁶⁷ and this also applies to al-Andalus. However, there was a case of anti-Jewish pogrom that took place in Granada in the eleventh century CE,⁶⁸ and in Almohad times the Jews suffered forced conversion and those suspected of being crypto-Jews were persecuted.⁶⁹ Despite the fact that in certain periods there was indeed an anti-Jewish sentiment among the Andalusī population, usury nevertheless goes

⁶⁵ This is a legal work by the Andalusī jurist al-‘Utbī (d. 254/868) which has been preserved thanks to Ibn Rushd al-Jadd’s commentary on it as analyzed by Ana Fernández Félix, *Cuestiones legales del Islam temprano. La “Utbiyya” y el proceso de formación de la sociedad islámica andalusí* (Madrid: CSIC, 2003). Thus, the text is found in Ibn Rushd al-Jadd, *al-Bayān wa-al-taḥṣīl wa-al-sharḥ wa-al-tawjīh wa-al-ta’līl fī al-masā’il al-mustakhrāja* (Beirut: Dār al-Gharb al-Islāmī, 1988), IV: 186.

⁶⁶ Spanish translation in Fernández Félix, *Cuestiones legales del Islam temprano*, 383.

⁶⁷ Mark Cohen, *Under crescent and cross. The Jews in the Middle Ages* (Princeton: University Press, 1994), xv–xx.

⁶⁸ Alejandro García Sanjuán, “Violencia contra los judíos: el pogromo de Granada del año 459 H/1066”, *De muerte violenta. Política, religión y violencia en al-Andalus*, ed. Maribel Fierro, [Estudios Onomástico-Biográficos de al-Andalus, XIV] (Madrid: CSIC, 2004), 167–207.

⁶⁹ See below note 81.

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unmentioned in the Muslim literature on the Jews contrary to what happened in Christian territories from the twelfth century onwards.

In both Muslim and Christian contexts, the appointment of Jews to positions of power seems to have been resorted to by Christian and Muslim rulers because they saw in them loyal servants on whom they could rely, for example, for the collection of taxes. The exegetist Peter Cantor (d. 1197) defined as usurers and as “*our Jews*” all those who occupied powerful positions at court and enjoyed the rulers’ protection, even those who were not actually Jewish.⁷⁰ For example, there were Christian money lenders, especially Italian merchants such as the Lombards.⁷¹ The role of the Jews as viziers and tax collectors in Islamic lands and royal money-lenders in Christendom has been regarded as a factor propitiating anti-Jewish sentiment among the population. But, as far as I have been able to ascertain, Jews are not mentioned as money-lenders to the rulers in Muslim sources.⁷² Jennifer Grayson, who studied the role of the Jews in the Abbasid court of Baghdad, states that, in spite of the preeminent role attributed by the economic historians to the courtly Jews in the global history of finance due to their financial activities, they should be understood as just “*middlemen in tax collection*”.⁷³ Moreover, although Abbasid viziers borrowed money at interest from wealthy merchants, both Jews and Gentiles,⁷⁴ this did not apparently propitiate the formation in this region of the stereotype of the Jewish usurer.

In al-Andalus, during the Taifa period in the fifth/eleventh century,⁷⁵ for instance, the Jews had the support of many of the Taifa kings, who appointed them to important positions in the court. Scholars such as Camilla Adang⁷⁶ and Alejandro García Sanjuán draw a correlation between the presence of Jews in court positions (and also in Muslim markets)⁷⁷ and the increasingly unfavourable public opinion towards them among

⁷⁰ Cornell, “In the Shadow”, 19. He refers to Nelson, *The Idea of Usury*, 10–1.

⁷¹ Maxime Rodinson, *Islam y Capitalismo*, trans. Marta Rojzman (Córdoba (Argentina): Siglo XXI Argentina Editores, 1973), 57.

⁷² I would like to thank Luke Yarbrough for his advice and the bibliography suggested. His impression is that the stereotype of Jews as usurers is mostly absent in the Islamic East. He has observed that Jews and Christians are commonly accused of becoming physicians in the courts and state secretaries in order to control Muslims, but this power is not usually exercised as private money-lenders, but through official positions. Luke B. Yarbrough, *Friends of the Emir. Non-Muslim State Officials in Premodern Islamic Thought* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2019), 154–5. Against the preeminent role attributed by the economic historians to the courtly Jews in the global history of finance due to their financial activities, Jennifer Grayson states that they should be understood as “*middlemen in tax collection*”. Besides, although Abbasid viziers borrowed money at interest from wealthy merchants, both Jews and Gentiles, this did not apparently propitiate the formation in this region of the stereotype of the Jewish usurer. Jennifer Grayson, “Unable to Dismiss Them”. Re-assessing the Jewish “Court Bankers” of Abbasid Baghdad, 908–932”, *Journal of the Economic and Social History of the Orient* 64 (2021), 25–54.

⁷³ Jennifer Grayson, “Unable to Dismiss Them”. Re-assessing the Jewish “Court Bankers” of Abbasid Baghdad, 908–932”, *Journal of the Economic and Social History of the Orient* 64 (2021), 25–54.

⁷⁴ Grayson, “Unable to Dismiss Them”, 49.

⁷⁵ According to Saleh Eazah Al-Zahrani, the stereotypes related to the Jews in al-Andalus started in this moment, but none of them referred to their economic activities. See Saleh Eazah Al-Zahrani, *Anaquel de Estudios Árabes* 31 (2020), 207–34, esp. 234.

⁷⁶ Camilla Adang, *Islam frente a judaísmo. La polémica de Ibn Ḥazm de Córdoba* (Madrid: Aben Ezra Ediciones, 1994), 15–23; Camilla Adang, *Muslim Writers on Judaism and the Hebrew Bible. From Ibn Rabban to Ibn Ḥazm* (Leiden: Brill, 1996).

⁷⁷ According to Camilla Adang, the tradition of ‘Umar b. al-Khaṭṭāb prohibiting that Jews and Christians acted as money-changers, and also as butchers in the Muslim markets, led to a discussion among the Mālikī scholars on whether *dhimmī*-s should be allowed to sell their food in the *sūq*-s, while the Zāhirī Ibn Ḥazm, in spite of his attacks against the other religions, considered permissible their presence in the markets, as well as their involvement in

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everyday Muslims. García Sanjuán quotes a fragment of the chronicle of Ibn al-Kardabūs in which the rulers’ practice of entrusting Muslim affairs to Jews is criticised,⁷⁸ as according to the *dhimma* pact, a Jew could not have a position of power over Muslims. But in Ibn al-Kardabūs’ chronicle or other historical writings no reference to possible usurious activities carried out by Jews is found. No reference is either found in the memoirs of the last Zīrid emir ‘Abd Allāh b. Buluggīn (r. 465/1073 - 482/1090),⁷⁹ who explained the reasons behind the appointment as a vizier of the Jew Abū ‘Abd Allāh Yūsuf b. Naghrīla (son of the also vizier Samuel ha-Nagid) by his grandfather Bādīs b. Ḥabūs (r. 428/1038-465/1073).⁸⁰

Ibn Ḥazm, a Zāhirī jurist and fierce author of the few extant works of religious polemical literature written in al-Andalus that have been preserved, personally attacked the vizier Yūsuf b. Naghrīla in his opuscle entitled *Radd Abī Muḥammad b. Ḥazm ‘alā Ibn al-Naghrīla al-yahūdī – la’anahu Allāhu* (Abū Muḥammad b. Ḥazm’s Refutation of Ibn al-Naghrīla the Jew – God damn him).⁸¹ He considered the Umayyads as the only legitimate rulers and opposed the Taifa kings, and especially their habit of appointing Jews as viziers, although ‘Abd al-Rahmān III and al-Ḥakam II had already entrusted the Jew Ḥasday b. Shaprūt in the times of the Umayyad caliphate with a high court position. And yet, while the eight chapters and conclusion of Ibn Ḥazm’s refutation are peppered with anti-Jewish insults and slander, the specific adjective “usurer” is not one of them.⁸² No references to possible usurious practices on the part of the Jews have been found in his other work, *al-Fiṣal fī-al-milal*. The fact that Ibn Ḥazm’s writings do not mention usury in this vein does not necessarily mean that Ibn Ḥazm could not have made a connection between usury and Jews in other texts that have not been preserved, but even in that case, it would be an exceptional appearance in comparison to the many allusions

interreligious partnerships. Camilla Adang, “Ibn Ḥazm’s Critique of some Judaizing tendencies”, *Medieval and Modern Perspectives on Muslim-Jewish Relations*, ed. Ronald L. Nettler (Oxford: Harwood Academic in Cooperation with the Oxford Centre for Postgraduate Hebrew Studies, 1995), 1–15, 6, n. 47, n. 48.

⁷⁸ García Sanjuán, “Violencia contra los judíos”, 170. He refers to Ibn al-Kardabūs, *Ta’rīkh al-Andalus*, ed. A. M. al-‘Abbadī (Madrid: Instituto de Estudios Islámicos, 1971), 78. Spanish translation in Felipe Maíllo, *Ibn al-Kardabūs. Historia de al-Andalus* (Madrid: Akal, 1986), 98–9.

⁷⁹ The memoirs of ‘Abd Allāh, the last Zīrid king of Granada, describe the reasons that led some Taifa kings to put Jews in positions of power; see *Mudhakkarāt al-amīr ‘Abd Allāh, ākhir mulūk banī Zīrī bi-Gharnāṭa (483-469) al-musamma bi-Kitāb al-tibyān*, ed. Évariste Lévi-Provençal (Cairo: Dār al-ma‘ārif, 1955, 31–2); English translation in *The Tibyān. Memoirs of ‘Abd Allāh b. Buluggīn last Zīrid Amīr of Granada*, trans. Amin T. Tibi, (Leiden: Brill, 1986), 56.

⁸⁰ We know of the existence of other Jewish viziers during the same period, some of whom ended up ultimately converting to Islam. Among the Jews of the Muslim courts there were Yequiel b. Ishāq b. Ḥasan, possibly vizier of Mundir II, of the Tujībīd court of Zaragoza; Ḥasday b. Shaprūt, who was a tax collector at the court of caliphs ‘Abd al-Rahmān III and al-Ḥakam II in Cordoba; Abū al-Faḍl b. Ḥasday b. Yūsuf, who acted as a vizier to three different Hūdīd rulers in Zaragoza; Abū Bakr b. Sadray, vizier to the last ruler of Albarracín; and Abū Ishāq Ibrāhīm b. Meir b. Muḥājir, known as Shurtmiqāsh, vizier at the ‘Abbādid court of Seville. There is also evidence of Jewish viziers in other kingdoms such as Valencia and Badajoz, and cases of former Jews who became viziers after converting to Islam, as in the case of Ibn al-Qarawī al-Islāmī, who acted as vizier to the Zīrids of Granada. Felipe Maíllo, “Los judíos en las fuentes andalusíes y magrebíes. Los visires”, *Studia Historica. Historia Medieval* 23 (2005), 221–49, 230–3.

⁸¹ Ibn Ḥazm wrote a refutation against a text by Ibn Naghrīla in which he had allegedly pointed to mistakes and contradictions in the Qur’ān. However, Ibn Ḥazm was unable to get his hands on a copy of Ibn Naghrīla’s text and instead employed a previous refutation made by another Muslim author in order to learn about its content.

⁸² *Zindīq, mā’iq, jāhil, waqqāh, anūk, ‘adīm al-‘aql, salīh al-tamyīz, maṭmūs, ‘ayn al-qalb, ḡalīm al-jahl, khasīs, majnūn*, etc. Spanish translation included in Emilio García Gómez, “Polémica religiosa entre Ibn Ḥazm e Ibn al-Naghrīla”, *al-Andalus* 4/1 (1936-1939), 1–28, 3 n. 7–8; 23; see also Maribel Fierro, “Ibn Ḥazm and the Jewish zindīq”, *Ibn Ḥazm. The Life and Works of a Controversial Thinker*, ed. Camilla Adang et al. (Leiden: Brill, 2013), 497–509.

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to the Jewish usurer in Christian anti-Jewish polemical works. Thus, this silence constitutes further evidence that, although during this period in Islamic Iberia we clearly find both court Jews and anti-Jewish sentiment, usury was not one of the various arguments levelled against Jews in Muslim religious polemics.

As already mentioned, between 539/1145 and 645/1248 the Almohads launched a campaign of religious homogenisation across al-Andalus. Not only were Christians and Jews forced to convert or flee, but Muslims, too, were obliged to embrace the specific Almohad understanding of Islam.⁸³ During this time many Arabised and culturally 'Islamicised' Jews moved to Christian lands. From the seventh/thirteenth century onwards, we again find Jews living in al-Andalus, this time under Naṣrid rule. Some of them had secretly kept their Jewish faith under the Almohad regime⁸⁴ and may have reverted to their birth religion after the fall of the Almohads. Some may have returned from exile after the dynasty's demise. It is in the eighth/fourteenth and ninth/fifteenth centuries, coinciding with their return, when references to usury practiced specifically by Jews first shows up in Muslim Andalusī texts.

The first of these references appears in a juridical question (*fatwā*) issued by the Granadan jurist Ibn Lubb (d. 782/1381), which was included in al-Wansharīsī's *Mi'yār* (VI, pp. 433-4):

[حكم معاملة اليهود]

وسئل عن معاملة اليهود، مع العلم بأن جميع معاملتهم أو غالبها على وجه الربى.

فأجاب: "حكم المسألة أن ينظر في معاملة، فإن لم يكن في ظاهرها فساد ولا ادعاه خصم، فالواجب العمل على الصحة".

He [Ibn Lubb] was consulted about commercial transactions with Jews, since all or most of their transactions take place in a usurious manner.

He replied: “*The legal consideration of the matter depends on examining each transaction, and if there is no corruption [fasād] in appearance, nor is there any suspicion [of such corruption], the duty is to act as if the transaction was correct*”.

The text reflects a concern that seems to come from a popular context, whereas Ibn Lubb replies that the corruption must not be taken for granted and recommends to examine each case individually.

⁸³ María Jesús Viguera, “I. Componentes y estructura de la población”, *Historia de España de Menéndez Pidal*, 30 vols. (Madrid: Espasa-Calpe, 1958-2000), VIII/4: 27–8; Maribel Fierro, “Again on Forced Conversion in the Almohad Period”, in *Forced Conversion in Christianity, Judaism and Islam*, ed. Mercedes García-Arenal and Yonatan Glazer-Eytan (Leiden: Brill, 2019), 111–32.

⁸⁴ Some Jews in fact never left Almohad lands: even if externally they behaved as Muslims, they kept their Jewish beliefs and practices in secret as recorded in both Muslim and Jewish sources. See for example al-Marrākushī (d. 702/1303), *al-Mu'jib fī talkhīṣ akhbār al-Maghrib*, (*The History of the Almohads*), ed. Reinhart Dozy (Leiden: Brill, 2nd ed. 1881), 223; Maimonides, *Sobre el Mesías. Carta a los judíos de Yemen. Sobre astrología. Carta a los judíos de Montpellier*, trans. Judit Targarona (Barcelona: Ropiedras Ediciones, 1987) and Viguera, “I. Componentes”, 27–8.

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The second reference appears in al-Shāṭibī’s aforementioned *mas’ala*:⁸⁵

”الله تعالى احل طعام اهل الكتب وغالبهم فيها التلبس بالمحرمات جمة كالنجاسات من الدم و الخمر و لحم الخنزير وانهم لا يتحفظون من سائر من النجاسات تحفظ اهل الاسلام ومع ذلك فاباحه الله باطلاق واجازه السلف الصالح و لا ان يكون على النجاسة او ما يحرم اكله بعامة معينة. وهكذا اكتسابهم للطعام الغالب عليها انها اثمان الخمر والخنزير والربا والسحت ومع ذلك فاباح طعامهم مطلقا والى هذا فانه تع اباح اخذ الجزية منهم وغالب الاكتساب من هذه الامور وبه استدل الطبري على صحة معاملة من لا يبالي من المسلمين من اين اكتسبت وادلة الشريعة كثيرة في هذا المعنى“.

”*God considered lawful the food of the People of the Books [ahl al-Kutub].⁸⁶ And yet, most of them regularly come into contact with forbidden substances [muḥarramāt] such as impurities [najāsāt] derived from blood, wine and pork, as they do not protect themselves from contamination in the way that Muslims do. In spite of this, God permitted it [to eat their food] in general [bi-itlāq], and the Salaf generation allowed it too, as long as the food itself was not proven to unmistakably contain something impure or forbidden. In the same way, although they obtain the majority of their assets via wine, pork, usury and unjustified profits, still He (blessings) permitted their food in general, and he allowed Muslims to take the jizya tax from them, although most of their goods derive from such activities. Based on this, al-Ṭabarī stated that it was permissible to perform economic transactions with those whose profits come from sources unknown to the Muslims. And the evidence of the Sharī‘a in this sense is abundant”.*

In this passage, Christians are associated with *ribā* just as much as Jews are. Al-Shāṭibī was reacting against a trend initiated in Almohad times, when Mālikism passed through a reformation process derived from the *anti-madhhab* inclinations of the Almohad doctrine.⁸⁷ This reformation implied that some Mālikī jurists rejected *taqlīd*, meaning that they were reluctant to follow the teachings of the late Mālikī-s, and they resorted to the Revealed sources of law and the early Mālikī sources instead.⁸⁸ Although al-Shāṭibī does not share the restrictive “Almohad approach” regarding interfaith relations,⁸⁹ and even considers them beneficial, his methodology is influenced by the *anti-madhhab* trend of the post-Almohad reformed Mālikism and, in order to justify his opinion, he resorted to the early jurisprudence of the times in which Muslims were a minority in the

⁸⁵ Al-Shāṭibī, *Mu‘āmalat* (MS 362/3, Casablanca: King Abdul Aziz Foundation), First section, fol. 1v.

⁸⁶ In reference to Christians and Jews.

⁸⁷ Maribel Fierro, “Doctrina y práctica jurídicas bajo los almohades”, *Los almohades. Problemas y perspectivas*, ed. M. Fierro, P. Cressier and L. Molina (Madrid: CSIC / Casa de Velázquez, 2005), 895–935, 917–8.

⁸⁸ For instance, according to Powers, al-Haskūrī (d. 653/1255) was one “of only a handful of scholars active during the Marīnid period who claimed the right to exercise *ijtihād*.” By circumventing some of the most commonly followed Mālikī opinions, al-Haskūrī turned – in what Powers refers to as “typical Almohadian fashion” – to early opinions as arguments for his own views. See Powers, *Law, Society and Culture in the Maghrib*, 92–3.

⁸⁹ The Almohads applied policies in this respect that differed from the *dhimma* system that had ensured the legal existence of Jewish and Christian communities under Muslim rule up to that moment. See Yohannan Friedmann, *Tolerance and coercion in Islam. Interfaith relations in the Muslim tradition* (Cambridge: Cambridge UP, 2003), 54–120.

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territories they had conquered, which was more tolerant with interfaith relations.⁹⁰ In al-Shāṭibī’s eyes, the restrictive juridical opinions regarding the economic activities with *dhimmī*-s were harmful for the Muslims who were in need of credit. In his opinion, Islamic jurisprudence (*fiqh*) should not imply a burden or a trouble, but it should bring benefits for the Muslim community.

The third and last relevant passage is another *fatwā*, this time by another Granadan jurist al-Ḥaffār (d. 811/1408)⁹¹ which was also included in al-Wansharīsī’s, *Mi’yār* (V p. 244):

[حكم معاملة اليهود]

وسئل “هل تجوز معاملة اليهود بالبيع والشراء منهم والاستدانة أو لا؟”

فأجاب: “إذا اشترى الرجل وباع من اليهود على ما يجوز شرعا ولا يعمل معه بربا ولا بوجه لا يسوغ في الشرع فذلك حلال طيب سائغ.”

He [al-Ḥaffār] was asked: “*Are the transactions of selling, buying and borrowing money from the Jews permitted?*”

He replied: “*If a man buys and sells from a Jew according to what is legally permitted, and neither ribā nor other of the transactions which are not allowed are practiced, it is legal, good and permitted*”.

Conclusions

In Latin Christendom, the emergence of the association between the usurious money-lending and the Jews seems to be related to the increasing reliance on credit derived from the economic and commercial revolution that took place during the twelfth and thirteenth centuries and the flourishing of the Mediterranean trade. It seems that heavy financial burdens during economic crises might have caused among the Christians an intense hostile reaction against money-loans and the derived interests taken, for example, in Castile.⁹² For some reason, this did not happen in Muslim Iberia but, unfortunately, the relative absence of credit documents al-Andalus⁹³ does not allow us

⁹⁰ Nurit Tsafir, “The attitude of Sunnī Islam toward Jews and Christians as reflected in some legal issues”, *Al-Qanṭara. Revista de Estudios Árabes* 26/2 (2005), 317–36.

⁹¹ Lehman followed the information provided by E. Amar when he attributed this text to Ibn Sirāj, a jurist whom he situates in fifth/eleventh-century Cordoba. Vincent Lagadère, however, states that this attribution is not correct, and that the text belongs to al-Ḥaffār. After taking a look at al-Wansharīsī’s *Mi’yār*, I think that the *fatwā* can be attributed either to al-Ḥaffār, or to a Naṣrid jurist also called Ibn Sirāj/Sarrāj. In both cases, though, the text can be contextualised in Naṣrid Granada. See Matthias B. Lehmann, “Islamic Legal Consultation and the Jewish-Muslim ‘Convivencia’: Al-Wansharīsī’s Fatwā Collection as a Source for Jewish Social History in al-Andalus and the Maghrib”, *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 6/1 (1999), 25–54, 46; Vincent Lagadère, *Histoire et Société en Occident Musulman au Moyen Âge. Analyse du Mi’yār d’al-Wanṣarīsī* (Madrid: Casa de Velázquez, CSIC, 1995), 184–86.

⁹² Soifer-Irish, “The Problem of Old Debts”, 282.

⁹³ Although the lack of documentary material for al-Andalus is not absolute, because we can find some samples of commercial contracts for instance in the Cairo Genizah, these are only transactions in which Jews were involved, while we cannot find archives as in the Ottoman administration. On the reasons for this lack of documentary archives, see the introduction by E. Manzano to the collective volume *From al-Andalus to Khurasan. Documents from the Medieval Muslim World*, ed. Petra M. Sijpesteijn, Lennart Sundelin, Sofía Torallas Tovar y Amalia Zomeño (Leiden, Boston: Brill, 2007). On the limits of this absence, see the studies by Marina Rustow, “A petition to a woman at the Fatimid court”, *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies* 73/1 (2010), 1–27, and *The Lost Archive. Traces of a Caliphate in a Cairo Synagogue* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2020), for whom the comparison

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neither to compare the amount of loans performed at the two sides of the frontier, nor to ascertain the extent to which Muslim populations were affected by the economic crises.

Because loans at interest have tended to be frowned upon across space and time, it was often “outsiders” who ended up specialising in this activity. We find examples as diverse as Greeks and other foreigners in modern Egypt, Hindu Banyan merchants in India, Jews and Lombards in medieval Europe, or Shansi bankers in China.⁹⁴ These minorities could easily end up being accused of being greedy and unfair in spite of the fact that whenever there was a more widespread need for credit, members of the majority group were generally quick to step in and take over. In any case, as regards the Jews living in Latin Christendom, according to Maristella Botticini and Zvi Eckstein, they engaged in urban skilled professions such as trading and money-lending since the twelfth century.⁹⁵ In different places of the Christian lands, the percentage of loans issued by Jews to the local bourgeoisie gradually increased throughout the twelfth and thirteenth centuries.⁹⁶ This type of trend probably contributed to the emergence of the image of the Jewish money-lender at the courts of Christian Europe and to the development of a related propaganda that put the blame on the Jews for situations of economic deprivation.⁹⁷

Nevertheless, the connection between Jews and usury has more to do with the construction in the Christian sphere of the figure of the “Other”. In this construction the fundamental point is not so much the reality of the practices that the Jews carried out,⁹⁸ but rather identifying distinctive elements in other religions or cultures that serve to extol what is praiseworthy in one’s own and reject what is attributed to the other as blameworthy.⁹⁹ As we have seen, this also happened in Muslim contexts, where Jews, but also Christians, were accused of practicing *ribā* but, still, we cannot talk about the existence of a parallel image of the “*dhimmī* usurer”, probably because certain sorts of interest-bearing loans, despite being morally frowned upon and theoretically prohibited, were sometimes needed, permitted and eventually considered as beneficial, instead of being perceived as a social evil or a financial obligation that could not be fulfilled.

Many studies have dealt with the relationship between the doctrine on the prohibition of usury in Judaism and the rise of capitalism.¹⁰⁰ This has to do with the broader debate about the influence of religion over the economy, but these works also seek to construct an argument that justifies the creation of the image of the Jewish usurer in the Middle

between medieval Europe and the Middle East is not valid due to the different nature of the documents produced in both societies.

⁹⁴ Rodinson, *Islam y Capitalismo*, 56–7.

⁹⁵ Maristella Botticini; Zvi Eckstein, “From Farmers to Merchants, Conversions and Diaspora. Human Capital and Jewish History”, *Journal of the European Economic Association* 5/5 (2007), 885-926, 923.

⁹⁶ See, for instance, Bensch, *Barcelona and its rulers*, 284.

⁹⁷ I would like to thank the reviewers their useful suggestions in this respect and, in general, their advice in relation to this and other aspects treated in the article.

⁹⁸ For a later period see Francesca Trivellato, *The Promise and Peril of Credit. What a Forgotten Legend about Jews and Finance Tells Us about the Making of European Commercial Society* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2019).

⁹⁹ On the construction of alterity see Nirenberg, *Communities of Violence*, and *Anti-Judaism: the Western tradition* (New York: W.W. Norton & Company, 2013).

¹⁰⁰ See, for instance, Werner Sombart, *The Jews and Modern Capitalism* (Kitchener, Ont.: Batoche, 2001).

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Ages. In the Christian sphere, the argument that in Judaism it is lawful to practice usury with Gentiles has been used to give basis to the theory that the image of the Jewish usurer arose because of actual pervasive money-lending on the part of Jews. However, in both Islam and Christianity there have been currents of opinion according to which it is permissible to lend money at interest to members of other religions. On its part, in spite of the general trend among the medieval Jewish jurists, according to which it was permissible to take or give interest to or from a Gentile,¹⁰¹ there was indeed some debate on the legality of such practices. For example, Izchak Abravanel (d. 1508) made a restrictive interpretation of the passage of the Torah that allows Jews to lend money at interest to Gentiles, arguing that the passage was referring specifically to the Canaanites, meaning that it was not lawful to lend at interest to other peoples.¹⁰²

In brief, in Islamic sources, the references to non-Muslims practicing *ribā* are few, and do not imply that Jews were the only ones who practiced usury, at least until modern and contemporary times.¹⁰³ In fact, in most of the texts here reviewed, non-Muslims living under Muslim rule (*dhimmī*-s) are mentioned and not just the Jews, so it can be concluded that there does not seem to exist in medieval times a recurring trope of the “Jewish usurer” in the Islamic imaginary. Thus, while we even find stories written in Christian contexts about Jewish usurers in the Muslim world, they are largely absent from the literature produced in *Dār al-Islām* itself. One such example is Bocaccio’s *The Three Rings*, in which a sultan asks a Jew from Alexandria to lend him money. In this story, the sultan and the Jew end up becoming friends, thus also illustrating the figure of the usurious Jew who exerts undue influence at court.

Under Naṣrid rule, al-Andalus, which consisted at that time of the current provinces of Almeria, Granada and Malaga, was suffering a progressive territorial decline derived from the pressure exerted by the Christian advance. Because the limited resources of the territory were insufficient to maintain the kingdom’s growing population, the Naṣrids increasingly relied on Mediterranean commerce and, in consequence, credit activities, which in some cases were performed by Jews.¹⁰⁴ In this context, while the religious affiliation of the people involved in the economic practices of Naṣrid Granada may perhaps have constituted an issue of concern for the common people, this was not true of the previously mentioned jurists, who showed a quite permissive attitude towards such interfaith transactions with the intention of promoting the overall economic welfare of the Muslim community within a general concern about *maṣlaḥa* (common

¹⁰¹ Aaron Kirschenbaum, “Jewish and Christian Theories of Usury in the Middle Ages”, *The Jewish Quarterly Review* 75/3 (1985), 270–89, 288.

¹⁰² Ariel Toaff, “Testi ebraici italiani relativi all’usura”, *Credito e usura fra teologia, diritto e amministrazione. Linguaggi a confronto (SEC. XII-XIV)*, ed. Diego Quaglioni, Giacomo Todeschini, Gian Maria Varanini [Collection de l’Ecole Française de Rome, 346] (Rome: École Française de Rome, 2005), 103–13.

¹⁰³ The image of the usurer Jew is, however, present nowadays in the Islamic context as well: Rachel Uziel, “Joking in the Ethnic Stereotypes, the Jewish Turkish usurer case”, *The Sephardi and Oriental heritage. Studies* (Jerusalem: Magnes Press, Hebrew University, 1982), 551–63.

¹⁰⁴ Adela Fábregas, “El reino Nazarí de Granada como área de comercio internacional: ¿Colonia mercantil o espacio de integración?”, *Anales de la Universidad de Alicante. Historia medieval* 18 (2012-2014), 153–69, 157; Adela Fábregas “Colaboradores necesarios. Comerciantes nazaríes y mercaderes extranjeros en el reino nazarí de Granada”, *eHumanista* 38 (2018), 116–30; José E. López de Coca Castañer, “Comercio exterior del reino de Granada”, *Actas del II Coloquio de Historia Medieval Andaluza. Hacienda y Comercio* (Seville: Diputación provincial de Sevilla, 1981), 335–77.

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welfare), since the transactions performed with Jews were apparently covering certain commercial and financial needs of the Muslims. According to some jurists, such as al-Shāṭibī, Islamic law should promote the common good (*maṣlaḥa*) of the Muslim community and, in consequence, *maṣlaḥa* became an important aspect in the rule-making process. Moreover, al-Shāṭibī considered it as the main purpose of God’s law.¹⁰⁵

It is in the *fatāwā* issued in Naṣrid Granada that a more specific connection between Jews and usury makes its appearance. The fact that this territorial shrinking Andalusī polity was often a vassal state of Castile may have helped the spread of the trope of the Jew as usurer: the constant embassies and delegations of Muslims in Christian lands and vice versa could have led to the spread and consolidation of such stereotype. Also, as mentioned, under Almohad rule there had been no Jews as such in al-Andalus, as they had all been forced to either convert or go into exile. Those who fled to the North could have performed there financial and commercial activities.¹⁰⁶ Had the Jews who lived in Naṣrid Granada¹⁰⁷ – the context of the *fatāwā* analysed here – returned from exile in Christian lands? And if they did, did their arrival mean an increase in the performance of money-loans at interest? If that was the case, their return could have constituted a matter of concern among the Muslim population. Whatever the origin for the image of the Jewish money-lender in Granada, it does not appear to have become part of religious anti-Jewish propaganda.

The issue of the usurious practices of non-Muslims is, in fact, mostly dealt within the Islamic legal sources, where the attitude of Muslim jurists towards the economic practices of the Jews seems to have been relatively neutral. In the texts analysed here from the Naṣrid period, as Lehmann had already noted, what we see is “*the primacy of economic pragmatism guiding the legal process*”.¹⁰⁸ This means that some activities which would have been condemned in previous periods were now allowed because they implied an overriding economic benefit for the community. As mentioned, *maṣlaḥa*, or common good, constitutes the basis on which al-Shāṭibī –author of one of the texts analysed – built his particular legal theory. Thus, as in some Christian contexts, the common good was employed to justify certain kinds of credit activities which should otherwise be banned. The prohibition of *ribā* had been traditionally conceived as the

¹⁰⁵ See Rami Koujah, “Maṣlaḥa as a Normative Claim of Islamic Jurisprudence. The legal philosophy of al-‘Izz b. ‘Abd al-Salām”, *Locating the Sharī‘a. legal fluidity in theory, history and practice*, ed. Sohaira Z. M. Siddiqui (Leiden: Brill, 2019), 127–50; Felicitas Opwis, *Maṣlaḥa and the Purpose of the Law. Islamic Discourse on Legal Change from the 4th/10th to 8th/14th Century* (Leiden: Brill, 2010).

¹⁰⁶ There is a debate on whether the Jews’ shift to this kind of professions was due to the restrictions imposed on them, or if it was a natural consequence of their intellectual activity as Botticini and Eckstein suggest. According to Eliyahu Ashtor, one of the reasons for the change in the professions of the Andalusī Jewish community is that in the fifth/eleventh century they were subjected to a series of persecutions, in which many had their businesses and belongings expropriated. In any case, their financial and commercial activities increased in number in this moment. Eliyahu Ashtor, *A Social and Economic History of the Near East in the Middle Ages* (London: Collins, 1976), 195; Botticini; Eckstein, “From Farmers to Merchants”, 923.

¹⁰⁷ Rachel Arié, *El reino nasrī de Granada* (Madrid: Mapfre, 1992), 146. On this, see also Malika Zemmama Squalli, *Les dhimmi juifs dans le royaume nasride de Grenade (1238-1492)*, Ph.D. Thesis, Université de Bordeaux III, 1998 (Lille: Atelier national de reproduction des thèses, 2003).

¹⁰⁸ Lehmann, “Islamic Legal Consultation”, 46. Although Lehmann refers in his article to the Taifa period, we think that his attribution of al-Ḥaffār’s *fatwā* to an eleventh-century jurist is wrong, and that such text in fact belongs to the Naṣrid context. All the similar texts referred to by Lehmann were written in Naṣrid times, as in the case of Ibn Lubb’s *fatwā*. In the Naṣrid period, economic pragmatism also played a relevant role in the rule-making process.

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basis of the Islamic moral economy but, in this moment, jurists such as al-Shāṭibī made an attempt to distinguish between legality and morality (*waraʿ*). In his view, the fact that a transaction was perceived as immoral was not enough to ban it from the legal point of view.¹⁰⁹

The difference, it seems, is that through the institutionalisation of certain credit activities, the Latin Church claimed a legal way of covering the credit necessities of the society with the aim of monopolising the profits derived from money-lending transactions. In this context, the Jews were seen as competitors. Since –as previously mentioned– Muslim authorities did not institutionalise similar activities, the *‘ulamāʿ*, who did not belong to a structured hierarchy like the Latin clergy, did not regard the Jews as their competitors, but as a group who could cover the credit needs of the Muslim community. This might explain their lack of interest in spreading the image of the “Jewish usurer”.

¹⁰⁹ Ahmad al-Raysuni et al., *Imam Al-Shatibi's Theory of the Higher Objectives and Intents of Islamic Law* (London, Washington: International Institute of Islamic Thought, 2005), 104.